

Indication Prioritization using TSR score in Early Drug Development

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Abstract

Identifying the appropriate indication for a newly developed compound is essential in early drug development. Since baseline and treatment patient data are often unavailable at this stage, we must rely on alternative, relevant data sources to infer the relationship between the indication and the compound. In oncology, transcriptomics combined with computational methods, such as connectivity scores in CMAP, have been successfully utilized to infer the effectiveness of cancer drugs through controlled large-scale in-vitro experiments. However, in the field of immunology and inflammation (I&I), such large-scale systematic resources are lacking. Instead, public transcriptomic data from heterogeneous platforms are available. To address this, we propose a novel parametric TSR score, which differs from the nonparametric rank-based GSEA-style statistic. This new score is tailored to the I&I drug development environment and the heterogeneous nature of public data, while aligning with key drug development principles, Proof of Mechanism and Proof of Concept.

Key Words: indication finding, indication expansion, transcriptome signature reversion, gene expression signature

1. Introduction

Identifying the appropriate indication for a newly developed drug is a crucial step in the early stages of drug development. In the field of immunology and inflammation (I&I), the concept of an initial indication arises as soon as drug developers start considering potential targets and corresponding compounds, which can be as early as the target identification stage. However, the selected indication is typically applied after patient recruitment in phase 2. This creates a time gap between the initial stage and phase 2, during which the study team can discuss and optimize the indication selection for the developed drug.

To optimize candidate indications, pharmaceutical industries generally employ multi-functional approaches to improve (or de-risk) the selection process, utilizing:

- Real-world data/evidence
- Scientific literature search
- In vitro artificial disease systems to simulate drug activity
- Public/private data related to candidate indications
- Competitor landscape information
- In-house trial information with similar drugs or indications

Transcriptomic analyses for determining drug activity based on artificial disease systems and matching this information to public or private disease data (3rd and 4th items above) can be effectively used to produce informative solutions for this optimization problem. In oncology, transcriptomics have been successfully used in this regard. In the CMAP project (Lamb et al.

2006), multiple cancer drugs were administered to numerous cancer cell lines in parallel to profile which drug matches which cancer type. The CMAP project devised a computational method called the connectivity score, which ranks candidate drugs for each cancer type (cell line) in a well-controlled experimental design and well-defined objective measure.

In the field of immunology and inflammation (I&I), however, such large-scale systematic resources are lacking. Instead, public transcriptomic data from heterogeneous platforms are available. In this context, we propose a novel parametric matching scoring scheme called the TSR score (TSR stands for transcriptome signature reversion, mentioned in (Koudijs et al. 2019)). This score differs from the nonparametric rank-based GSEA-style statistic (see (Subramanian et al. 2005) for GSEA) and is tailored to the I&I drug development environment and the heterogeneous nature of public data, while aligning with key drug development principles, such as Proof of Mechanism and Proof of Concept (EUPATI (2015b)).

2. Methods

2.1 Definition and Types of Signature

To develop a matching score, we first need to clarify what a signature means in the context of transcriptomics. The term has been widely used in literature but typically refers to a list of gene names. Here, we specify and extend the traditional definition of a signature to include two components: 1. differentially expressed genes (or a list of genes selected based on predefined criteria) between two experimental conditions, and 2. fold-change information with associated uncertainty (e.g., fold-change estimates and their standard errors). The purpose of this extended definition is to emphasize the direct use of fold-change values in matching signatures, which is often overlooked in traditional matching schemes (e.g., connectivity score). Additionally, the definition can be further extended to the pathway level, encompassing a list of differential pathways with pathway scores (e.g., activation z-score).

Depending on the comparison between the two experimental conditions, various types of signatures are possible. For indication finding in I&I drug development, we are primarily interested in the drug's activity against a particular disease. Therefore, the following three types of signatures are most relevant, as shown in Figure 1: compound (or drug) signature, disease signature, and target signature.

Figure 1: Three main types of signatures. Compound Signature: Derived from comparing post-treatment samples to pre-treatment samples. Disease Signature: Obtained by comparing baseline samples to healthy control samples. This can also include paired comparisons, such as lesional vs. non-lesional skin in skin diseases. Target Signature: Generated by comparing samples stimulated by a drug target to unstimulated samples in an artificial disease system. This can serve as a surrogate for a disease signature (diseased vs. healthy) when patient data for a specific indication are unavailable, which is often the case in the early stages of drug development.

2.2 TSR Score

The TSR (transcriptome signature reversion, (Koudijs et al. 2019)) score is a novel computational method designed to measure the degree of matching between two signatures (e.g., compound signature vs. disease signature). The score ranges from -1 to 1, similar to the Pearson correlation coefficient: -1 indicates the best match for a reversion pattern between the two signatures, while +1 indicates the best match for a concordance pattern. When comparing a disease signature and a compound signature, we expect a reversion of the signature (i.e., inhibition of gene expression post-treatment that was activated pre-treatment), so a score closer to -1 represents a better match.

Figure 2 illustrates an example with three signatures, demonstrating how the transcriptome signature is reversed after treatment. As shown by their fold-changes, the direction of activation (or inhibition) is exactly opposite to the direction of the compound signature, although the magnitude of reversion differs between the two drugs. The TSR score is developed to summarize the matching between two signatures, as depicted in the figure.

Figure 2: One target and two compound signatures. On the left, the target signature consists of about 100 genes, derived from comparing stimulated samples to unstimulated samples. More than half of the top genes were up-regulated (activated) compared to the unstimulated samples, while less than half were down-regulated (inhibited). In the middle and on the right are the compound signatures, showing the fold-changes of the corresponding genes in the target signature for two different drugs (Drug A and Drug B). Both drugs target the same molecule used for stimulation, but 'Drug B' demonstrates a better reversion pattern than 'Drug A' in terms of the magnitude of the reversion.

Mathematically, the TSR score is an average score across multiple genes in the signature. To understand the TSR score, we first need to understand the matching of a single gene between two signatures. Let X be the estimated log fold-change to be compared (e.g., fold-change in compound signature) to a reference log fold-change μ (e.g., fold-change in disease signature), and let Y be a matching ordinal variable taking values of -1 , 0 , or 1 . In this setup, the TSR for a single gene is the expected value of Y under a parametric assumption: the estimated fold-change X , conditioned on the matching variable Y , is normally distributed

$$X|Y = k \sim N(\mu_k, \sigma)$$

where $\mu_{-1} = -\mu$, $\mu_0 = 0$, and $\mu_1 = \mu$. The probability of the matching variable Y given $X = x$ is then calculated as

$$\Pr(Y = k|x) = \frac{\pi_k \Pr(x|Y = k)}{\sum_{j=-1,0,1} \pi_j \Pr(x|Y = j)}$$

where the prior probability of Y is given as $\pi_k = 1/3$ for $k = -1,0,1$. For N genes, matching score is calculated as the average of expectations of N Y values as

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N E[Y_i | x_i, \mu_i, \sigma_i]$$

. For σ_i of the fold-change estimate x_i , we use the standard error of x_i in the calculation of TSR score.

Unlike the correlation coefficient, the TSR score produces two different values depending on the reference (μ) and the evaluated (x). For example, when comparing signature A with signature B, we can evaluate signature A (x) against signature B (μ) or vice versa. Specifically, if these two signatures are a disease signature and a compound signature, we can assess two key clinical principles: Proof of Concept and Proof of Mechanism in the context of transcriptomics.

- **Evaluating Disease Signature:** Here, the compound signature is used as the reference (μ) and the disease signature is evaluated (x). Since the genes in the reference represent those related to the mechanism of the compound, evaluating the disease signature reflects how the genes involved in the drug's mechanism behave in the disease of interest. This assesses Proof of Mechanism at the transcriptomic level.
- **Evaluating Compound Signature:** In this case, the disease signature is used as the reference (μ) and the compound signature is evaluated (x). Since the genes in the reference represent disease-specific genes, evaluating the compound signature reflects how the compound acts on the disease. This assesses Proof of Concept for the disease at the transcriptomic level.

Figure 3 shows an example of TSR evaluation of pairs of target and compound signatures in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Dumbbell plot for comparison pairs in Figure 2. For each pair of target signature ‘Stim|Unstim’ and two compound signatures ‘Post|Pre, Drug A’ and ‘Post|Pre, Drug B’, each signature (target in yellow, compound in blue) is evaluated against the other signature. In Figure 2, the target signature (left) is used as the reference, and the two compound signatures (‘Drug A’ and ‘Drug B’) are evaluated and shown here. The TSR score for ‘Post|Pre, Drug A’ against ‘Stim|Unstim’ is 0.5, while for ‘Post|Pre, Drug B’ against ‘Stim|Unstim’ it is around -1, indicating a better match of the target signature to the compound signature ‘Drug B’ compared to ‘Drug A’. Evaluation of target signature against each compound signature is also shown in yellow.

3. Results

We demonstrate how the TSR score method can be used to explore the relationship between compounds and diseases using public gene expression databases. First, we collected gene expression datasets from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO, (Clough and Barrett 2016)) using keywords related to the given indication and compound. For each dataset collected, we performed differential expression analysis to extract signatures (either disease or compound), considering other experimental parameters (e.g., tissue origin).

Figure 4 shows 60 TSR score pairs between one compound signature and 60 disease signatures. The pairs were sorted according to the average of the two TSR scores for each pair. Pairs with TSR scores closer to -1 indicate better matching, suggesting that the patient populations in the rightmost pairs, for example, might be interesting potential target populations for the compound.

Figure 4: An illustration of the TSR scoring method with one compound signature and 60 disease signatures from public data base (GEO). TSR scores for each pair of disease and compound signatures are shown as paired circles in red and blue. The blue circle represents the evaluation of the compound against the disease (related to Proof of Concept), while the red circle represents the evaluation of the disease against the compound (related to Proof of Mechanism). The paired TSR scores are sorted, with pairs on the right (closer to -1) indicating better matching than those on the left (closer to 0)

4. Conclusions and Discussion

Indication selection is a critical step in the early drug development process, directly impacting the probability of success in subsequent studies. Due to the limited availability of patient data to infer drug activity for candidate indications in the early phase, pharmaceutical companies utilize multiple resources to maximize success rates. In this context, we propose the TSR score method, which uses transcriptomics to match disease and compound signatures for assessing drug effectiveness before phase 2 in early I&I drug development. The TSR score, a new parametric signature matching method, is informative as it can rank candidate indications against the developed drug (or drugs of interest) and is well-suited for heterogeneous public gene expression data. This method provides valuable information for key clinical decisions, such as ‘‘Proof of Mechanism’’ and ‘‘Proof of Concept,’’ at the transcriptomic level.

The utility of the TSR-based indication strategy extends beyond early-stage indication finding; it can also be used to explore indication expansion for already marketed drugs in later stages. For instance, many successful biologic treatments in the I&I field (see (Muñoz-Bellido, Moreno, and Dávila 2022)) have demonstrated effectiveness across diverse indications. The TSR matching approach can also investigate pathway-level activity by measuring its scores (e.g., normalized enrichment score, activity z-score (Krämer et al. 2014)) from differential analysis, elucidating disease activity or drug mechanisms of action, and enabling potential expansion to broader indications.

Currently, the method is exploratory and experimental. Future improvements should focus on better understanding the statistical properties of the TSR method, providing statistical significance (or guidance and interpretation) for TSR values, and investigating differences with standard GSEA-based signature matching methods (e.g., connectivity score).

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by Sanofi. We extend our gratitude to our Sanofi colleagues, Lin Ben, Dany Nassar, Christian Asbrand, Winnie Tung, Xuan Wang, Meiyue Wang, Lin Yong, Rui Wang, Tejaswi Iyyanki, Heming Xing, Innocent Agueusop, Wenting Wang for their thoughtful comments and discussions.

Conflict of interests

Kyung In Kim is an employee of Sanofi and may hold shares and/or stock options in the company.

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